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PEST ORGANISMS THREATENING EUROPE

XF-ACTORS

XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA ACTIVE CONTAINMENT
THROUGH A MULTIDISCIPLINARY-ORIENTED RESEARCH STRATEGY

3RD JOINT ANNUAL MEETING

Xylella Fastidiosa Active Containment Through a
multidisciplinary-Oriented Research Strategy

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

AJACCIO (FRANCE), 28–30 OCTOBER 2019

**PALAIS DES CONGRÈS, QUAI L'HERMINIER
AJACCIO, FRANCE**

THE EVENT WAS PART OF THE SECOND SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE ON ONGOING RESEARCH INTO *X. FASTIDIOSA* CO-ORGANISED WITH EUROPEAN FOOD SAFETY AUTHORITY (EFSA), H2020-MSCA-RISE PROJECT 734353 'CURE-XF', COST ACTION CA16107 'EUROXANTH', FRENCH NATIONAL INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH (INRA), FRENCH AGENCY FOR FOOD, ENVIRONMENTAL AND OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY (ANSES), EUPHRESKO, OFFICE DE L'ENVIRONNEMENT DE LA CORSE-DEPARTMENT CONSERVATOIRE BOTANIQUE NATIONAL DE CORSE (OEC-CNBC)

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Poster

Methylobacterium* spp., endophytes of olive trees, as potential biocontrol agents of *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca

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Abstract: Interactions between endophytes and plants can promote the health of the host and play a significant role in low-input sustainable agriculture. Understanding this plant–microbe interaction and the mechanisms that enable endophytes to enhance the plant defence response is essential, especially for endophytic bacteria that show biocontrol potential against vascular wilt pathogens. Investigations on the bacterial endophytic population occurring in the xylem of healthy and *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* ST53 (XfpST53)-infected olive trees showed that under field conditions, the population level of cultivable endophytic bacteria is highly variable, being mainly affected by the host genotype, host age, and wilting severity. Among the different cultivable bacteria occurring in the wood of olive trees, *Methylobacterium* spp. are one of the most interesting groups. *Methylobacterium* strains isolated from the xylem of healthy and XfpST53-infected olive trees have been identified as *M. mesophilicum* and *M. radiotolerans*. Species of *Methylobacterium* have also been reported as potential biocontrol agents, plant-growth-promoting bacteria, and resistance inducers, by producing phytohormones, inducing plant systemic resistance, and supplying or mobilising nutritional elements (siderophore production). In order to evaluate the potential of *M. mesophilicum* GR19, and *M. radiotolerans* GR18, GR22 e GR23, as nutrient competitors of XfpST53, the production of siderophores was investigated by using the Chrome Azurol S (CAS) agar and ferric perchlorate assay to detect hydroxamates. *M. mesophilicum* DSM 1708 and *M. radiotolerans* DSM 1819 were used as reference strains. All the tested strains produced different levels of siderophores, and the most effective were applied by endotherapy in healthy and XfpST53-infected olive trees, in order to evaluate *in planta* their activity in containing the olive quick decline syndrome. Moreover, the characterisation of plant-growth-promoting traits of several *Methylobacterium* strains are currently in progress, i.e. by screening the production of indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), and the 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate (ACC) deaminase activity.